

CONTENT ANALYSIS OF MEDICINES USED IN OPHTHALMIC DISEASES

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Abstract. *An analysis of the range of drugs used in ophthalmic diseases registered in the Republic of Uzbekistan showed that they are represented in the pharmaceutical market of Uzbekistan by such dosage forms as oral solutions, solutions for drops, ointments and gels. The number of registered medicines in the State Register for 2022 amounted to 104 items. Content analysis was used as a technique. The main objective of the ongoing study of the pharmaceutical market is to determine the share of domestic manufacturers in connection with the adoption of appropriate measures by government authorities to develop domestic pharmaceutical manufacturers.*

Keywords: *content-analysis, assortment, medicines used in ophthalmic diseases, essential drugs list, state register of medicines.*

INTRODUCTION. Ophthalmology is a field of medicine that studies the eye, its anatomy, physiology and diseases, as well as developing methods for the treatment and prevention of eye diseases. The eye (Latin oculus) is a sensory organ (organ of the visual system) of humans and animals, which has the ability to perceive electromagnetic radiation in light wavelength range and providing the function of vision. In humans, about 90% of the information from the outside world comes through the eye. The development of the visual system reaches maturity at the age of about 20 years and remains stable until the age of 30, with the exception of cases when changes in vision may occur in women during pregnancy. For this reason, at this stage of life, the replacement of glasses and contact lenses is negligible.

The most common vision problems in adults under 40, at this age, in addition to refraction (nearsightedness, farsightedness and astigmatism), eye injuries are a fairly common problem. About 75% of eye injuries occur in men between the ages of 18 and 40. Half of these injuries occur at home, often while doing repairs or playing sports, which can be avoided by using special eye protection techniques (safety glasses).

The modern pharmaceutical market of Uzbekistan is characterized by a steady growth in the product range. During the last decade there have been significant expansions, replenishment and deepening of the range of all major groups of medical and pharmaceutical products.

METHODS. **To conduct this study, the data provided in the State Register of medicines, medical devices and medical equipment approved for use in medical practice in the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2022 (No. 26) were used.**

RESULTS. This publication studied the range of medicines used for ophthalmic diseases registered in the Republic of Uzbekistan.

The range of medicines used for ophthalmic diseases in the State Register for 2022 is represented by 104 assortment positions, manufacturers of such dosage forms as drops, ointment and gel.

Table 1 presents domestically produced medicines used for ophthalmic diseases, included in the State Register of Uzbekistan for 2022.

Table 1

Medicines used in ophthalmic diseases of domestic production, registered in the Republic of Uzbekistan

№	The name of drug	Dosage form	Manufacturer
1	MR Taufon Taurine	Eye drops 40mg/ml 5 ml, 10 ml (dropper bottles)	Merrymed Farm, LLS Uzbekistan
2	Kerotrop Comb.drug (Carboxymet hylcellulosa Sodium,Glyc erin)	Eye drops 10 ml N1 (bottles- droppers)	Aseptica, LLS Uzbekistan
3	Monodeks Dexamethaso ne	Eye drops 0.05%, 0.1% 5 ml, 10 ml (polymer vials)	Aseptica, LLS Uzbekistan
4	Pressimol Timolol maleat	Eye drops 0.25%, 0.5% 5 ml (dropper bottles)	Jurabek Laboratories, JS LLS Uzbekistan
5	Rekbrinzan Brinzolamide	Eye drops, suspension 10 mg/ml 5 ml N1 (vials)	REKA-MED FARM, LLS Uzbekistan
6	Taumed Taurine	Eye drops 2%, 4% 5 ml, 10 ml (polymer bottles with cork dropper)	Aseptica, LLS Uzbekistan
7	Taurin Taurin	Eye drops 40 mg/ml 5 ml, 10 ml (vials)	Reka-Med Farm, JSV Uzbekistan
8	Taufon JL Taurine	Eye drops 4% 5 ml, 10 ml (dropper bottles)	Jurabek Laboratories, JSV Uzbekistan
9	Timalol Timolol	Eye drops 0.25%, 0.5% 5 ml, 8 ml, 10 ml (vials)	Dentafill Plyus, LLS Uzbekistan
10	Timobrinzol Comb.drug (Brinzolamid e, timolol)	Eye drops, suspension 5 ml (dropper bottles)	REKA-MED FARM, JSV Uzbekistan
11	Timolol Timolol maleate	Eye drops 0.25%; 0.5% 5 ml, 10 ml N1 (vials)	Reka-Med Farm, JSV Uzbekistan
12	Timopress	Eye drops 0.25%, 0.5% 5 ml, 10 ml (polymer vials)	Aseptica, LLS Uzbekistan

	Timolol maleate*		
13	Tobradrop - DX Comb.drug (Tobramycin, Dexamethasone)	Eye drops 5 ml, 10 ml (bottles-droppers)	Aseptica, LLS Uzbekistan
14	Sinozol Comb.drug (Zinc sulfat, boric acid)	Eye drops 10 ml N1 (dropper bottles)	Aseptica, LLS Uzbekistan
15	SiproMER Ciprofloxacin	Eye drops 3 mg/ml, 5 ml (dropper bottles)	Merrymed Farm, LLS Uzbekistan
16	Emoksikam Methylethylp iridinol hydrochlorid e	Eye drops 1% 5 ml (vials)	MEDIOFARM, LLS Uzbekistan
17	Emotrop Methylethylp iridinol	Eye drops 1% 5 ml N1 (bottles-droppers)	Aseptica, LLS Uzbekistan
18	Taufon-MF Taurine	Eye drops 4% 10 ml (vials)	Mediofarm, LLS Uzbekistan

As can be seen from the data in Table 1, an analysis of the range of medicines used for ophthalmic diseases included in the State Register of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2022 showed that medicines of domestic manufacturers are 18 items in drops (vials)

Fig.1 Quantitative ratio of registered medicines used in ophthalmic diseases.

The diagram shows the quantitative ratio of registered medicines used in ophthalmic diseases of domestic production.

Table 2 presents medicines used for ophthalmic diseases produced in the CIS countries, included in the State Register of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2022.

Table 2

Medicinal products of manufacturers of the CIS countries, used in ophthalmic diseases, registered in the Republic of Uzbekistan

№	Name of drug	Dosage form	Manufacturer
1	Aktipol M Aminibenzoic acid	Eye drops 0.007% 5 ml N1 (dropper bottles)	AKTI-M, NPMP, LLC by Slavyanskaya pharmacy, LLC Russia
2	Betaxolin Betaxolol	Eye drops 0.5% 5 ml N1 (bottle - droppers)	Groteks, LLC Russia
3	ViziDol Ketorolac	Eye drops 0.5% 5 ml N1 (bottle)	Likvor, CJSC Armenia
4	Viksipin Methylethylpiridinol	Eye drops 1% 5 ml, 10 ml (vials)	Groteks, LLC Russia
5	Hydrocortisonum Hydrocortisone	Eye ointment 0.5% 3 g, 5 g (tubes)	Tathhimpharmaceuticals, Russia
6	Dorzolan®Solo Dorzolamide	Eye drops 20 mg/ml 5 ml N1 (vials)	Groteks, LLC Russia
7	Dorzolan®Extra Comb.drug (Dorzolamide + Timolol)	Eye drops 20 mg/ml + 5 mg/ml 5 ml N1 (vials)	Groteks, LLC Russia
8	Lanotan Latanoprost	Eye drops 0.05 mg/ml 2.5 ml N1 (bottle - droppers)	Farmak, PJSC Ukraine
9	Mydoptic Phenylephrine*	Eye drops 2.5% 10 ml N1, N10 (bottle - dropper polyethylene)	Likvor, JSV Armenia
10	Oftimol Timolol	Eye drops 5 mg/ml 5 ml, 10 ml (vials)	Farmak, PJSC Ukraine
11	Oftimol Timolol	Eye drops 5 mg/ml 5 ml, 10 ml	Farmak, PJSC Ukraine

		(vials)	
12	Pilocarpinum Pilocarpine*	Eye drops 1% 5 ml (vials)	Sintez, LLC Russia
13	Sigida kristall Naphazoline	Eye drops 0.05% 0.4 ml N10, N20, N30 (dropper tube)	Groteks, LLC Russia
14	Taurinum Taurine	Eye drops 4%, 5 ml, 10 ml (dropper bottle)	Dosfarm, TOO Kazakhstan
15	Taurinum-AKOS Taurine	Eye drops 4% 5 ml (bottle - droppers)	Sintez, LLC Russia
16	Taufon Taurin	Eye drops 40 mg/ml 5 ml N3, 10ml N1 (vials complete with dropper cap)	GNTsLS, JSV produced by Pharmex Group, LLC Ukraine
17	Taufon Taurine	Eye drops 40 mg/ml 10 ml (vials)	Farmak, PJSC Ukraine
18	Thiotriazolinum Thiotriazoline*	Eye drops 10 mg/ml 5 ml (vials with dropper cap)	GNTsLS OZ, LLC Ukraine
19	Emoxi optik Metiletilperidinol*	Eye drops 1% 5 ml (vials)	Sintez, LLC Russia
20	Emoksipin Emoxypine	Solution, eye drops 10 mg/ml 5 ml N1 (bottle with cap dropper)	Belmedpreparaty, Republican unitary enterprise Belarus
21	ViziPres Dorzolamide	Eye drops 2% 5 ml (bottle droppers)	Likvor, CJSC Armenia

As can be seen from the data in Table 2, an analysis of the range of medicines used for ophthalmic diseases included in the State Register of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2022 showed that medicines from the CIS countries comprise 21 items, of which 20 are eye drops (vials), 1 ointment.

The results of the study showed that in the range of drugs used in ophthalmic diseases of domestic production there are drops (bottle) and ointment.

Fig.2 Quantitative ratio of registered medicines used in ophthalmic diseases.

The diagram shows the quantitative ratio of registered medicines used for ophthalmic diseases in the CIS countries.

The aim of the study was to study the range of composition of medicines used for ophthalmic diseases manufactured in the CIS countries registered in the Republic of Uzbekistan.

For a deeper and more comprehensive study of the range of drugs used in ophthalmic diseases, registered drugs used in foreign countries were also studied.

Table 3

Medicinal products of foreign manufacturers used for ophthalmic diseases registered in the Republic of Uzbekistan

№	Name of drug	Dosage form	Manufacturer
1	ROHTO® MOISTURIZING (Ronto) Hydroxyethylcellulose	Eye drops 0.6% 13 ml (dropper bottles)	Rohto Pharmaceutical Co., Ltd., Japan manufactured by: Rohto-Mentholatum (Vietnam) Co.,Ltd Vietnam
2	Azarga Comb.drug (Brinzolamide, Timolol)	Drops eye suspension (10 mg/ml + 5 mg/ml) 5 ml each (dropper bottle)	Novartis Pharma AG, Switzerland Produced by: s.a. Alcon Couvreur n.v. Belgium
3	AZOPT Brinzolamide	Eye drops 10 mg/ml, 5 ml (dropper bottle)	Novartis Pharma AG, Switzerland Produced by: s.a. Alcon Couvreur n.v. Belgium
4	Aykul Sodium carboxymethyl cellulose	Eye drops 0.5% 10 ml (bottles- droppers)	Axa Parental Ltd India
5	Akvatim Timolol	Eye drops 0.5% 5 ml (dropper bottles)	Aquarius Enterprises, India Produced by: East African (India) Overseas India
6	Akvatsipro-D Comb.drug (Ciprofloxacin, Dexamethasone)	Drops eye / ear 5 ml N1 (dropper bottles)	Aquarius Enterprises, India made by: East Africa (India) Overseas India
7	Aksadeks-M Comb.drug (Moxifloxacin hydrochloride, dexamethasone)	Eye drops 0.5%/0.1% 10 ml N1 (vials))	AXA PARENTERALS LTD India
8	Apisopt Plus Comb.drug (Dorzolamide, Timolol)	Eye drops 20 mg/ml+5 mg/ml 5 ml (dropper bottles)	Amman Pharmaceutical Industries Co. Jordan

9	Arutimol Timolol	Eye drops 0.25%; 0.5% 5 ml (vials)	Baush Health, Ltd., Russia produced by: Dr.Gerhard Mann Chem.-Pharm. Fabric GmbH Germany
10	Bimoptik Plus Romfarm Comb.drug (Bimatoprost, timolol)	Eye drops 0.3 mg/ml + 5 mg/ml 3 ml N1, N3 (dropper bottles)	S.C. Rompharm Company S.R.L. Romania
11	Blotim Timolol maleate	Eye drops 0.5%, 5 ml (vials)	REMINGTON PHARMACEUTICAL INDUSTRIES (PVT) LTD Pakistan
12	Brineks Brinzolamide	Eye drops 1% 5 ml N1 (bottle with dropper cap)	Sentiss Pharma Pvt. Ltd India
13	Brinzoks Brinzolamide	Eye drops 1%, 5 ml (dropper bottle)	Ajanta Pharma Limited India
14	Brinzopt Plus Comb.drug (Brinzolamide, timolol)	Eye drops 10 mg/ml + 5 mg/ml 5 ml (dropper bottles)	S.C. Rompharm Company S.R.L. Romania
15	Brinzopt Brinzolamide	Eye drops, suspension 10 mg/ml 5 ml (dropper bottle)	S.C. Rompharm Company S.R.L. Romania
16	BRITIM (britim) Comb.drug (Brimonidine*, Timolol)	Eye drops 5 ml (bottles droppers)	REMINGTON PHARMACEUTICAL INDUSTRIES (PVT) LTD Pakistan
17	Vizin Tetryzoline hydrochloride	Eye drops 0.05% 15 ml N1 (dropper bottles)	Johnson & Johnson LLC, Russia manufactured by: Janssen Pharmaceutics N.V. Belgium
18	Glaumaks Plus Comb.drug (Dorzolamide, Timolol)	Eye drops 20 mg/ml + 5 mg/ml N1 (vials)	JARDAN-GALENSKI LABORATORIJ d.d. Croatia
19	DEXOFORT® Comb.drug (Dexamethasone, ofloxacin)	Eye drops 1 mg + 3 mg / 1 ml, 5 ml (dropper bottle)	Sante (Private) Limited., Pakistan Made: Elko Organization (Pvt.) Ltd Pakistan

20	DITREF Comb.drug (Polyethylene glycol, propylene glycol)	Eye drops 15 ml N1 (dropper bottles)	World Medicine İlaç San. ve tick. A.Ş. Türkiye
21	Dorzopt Plus Comb.drug (Dorzolamide, timolol)	Eye drops 20 mg/ml + 5 mg/ml, 5 ml each (dropper bottle)	S.C. Rompharm Company S.R.L. Romania
22	Dukressa Comb.drug (Dexamethasone, Levofloxacin)	Eye drops 1 mg/ml+5 mg/ml 5 ml N1 (vials)	Santen OY, Finland issuing control quality: Santen OY, Finland, produced: Tubilux Pharma S.P.A. Italy
23	Duoprost Comb.drug (Latanoprost, timolol)	Eye drops 2.5 ml (dropper bottle)	S.C. Rompharm Company S.R.L. Romania nia
24	Intramol Timolol	Eye drops 0.5% 5 ml N1 (dropper bottles)	Beximco Pharmaceuticals Ltd Bangladesh
25	Iobrim Brimonidine tartrate	Eye drops 5 ml (bottles- droppers)	FDC LIMITED India usha
26	Iotim-B Comb.drug (Brimonidine, Timolol)	Eye drops 5 ml N1 (dropper bottles)	FDC Limited India
27	Cardexin Comb.drug (Dexamethasone, neomycin)	Drops eye and ear 0.1% + 0.5% 5 ml each (dropper bottles)	KARAN HEALTHCARE (P) LTD, India manufactured by: ALPA LABORATORIES LTD India
28	Cataxol Azapentacene*	Eye drops 0.015% 15 ml N1 (dropper bottles)	World Medicine Ophthalmics İlaçları Ltd. Sti., Turkey produced by: World Medicine İlaç San. ve Tic. A.S. Türkiye
29	CATARAX Azapentacene*	Eye drops-solution 0.015% 15 ml (dropper bottle)	S.C. Rompharm Company S.R.L. Romania

30	KO-DORZAL Comb.drug (Dorzolamide, Timolol)	Eye drops 5 ml (dropper bottles)	Sante (Private) Limited Pakistan
31	KORNEREGEL Dexpanthenol	Eye gel 50 mg/g 5 g (tubes)	Baush Health, Ltd., Russia produced by: Dr.Gerhard Mann Chem.-pharm. Factory GmbH Germany
32	XALANOL Comb.drug (Timolol maleate, Latanoprost)	Eye drops 2.5 ml (dropper bottles)	Beximco Pharmaceuticals Ltd Bangladesh
33	Xalaprost Latanoprost	Eye drops 0.005% 2.5 ml (dropper bottles)	Beximco Pharmaceuticals Ltd Bangladesh
34	XALATHAN® Latanoprost	Eye drops 0.005% 2.5 ml (vials)	Pfizer HCP Corporation, USA, USA made: Pfizer MFG. Belgium N.V. Belgium
35	XOLATIM Comb.drug (Dorzolamide hydrochloride, Timolol)	Eye drops 20 mg/ml+5 mg/ml 5 ml (dropper bottles)	Deva Holding A.S. Türkiye
36	LAKOMA Latanoprost	Eye drops 0.005% 2.5 ml (vials)	Ajanta Pharma Limited India
37	L-DEXOPT Comb.drug (Levofloxacin,dexam ethasone phosphate)	Eye drops 5 mg/ml + 1 mg/ml 5 ml (dropper bottle)	S.C. Rompharm Company S.R.L. Romania
38	LOPROSTAN Comb.drug (Latanoprost + timolol)	Eye drops 0.005% + 0.5% 2.5 ml N1 (dropper bottle)	Amman Pharmaceutical Industries Иордания
39	MAXITROL® Comb.drug (Dexamethasone, neomycin, polymyxin B)	Eye drops 5 ml (dropper bottle)	Novartis Pharma AG, Switzerland Produced by: s.a. Alcon Couvreur n.v. Belgium
40	MEDETROM Comb.drug (Tobramycin, Dexamethasone)	Eye drops, suspension 3 mg/ml + 1 mg/ml 5 ml N1 (dropper bottles)	World Medicine Ophthalmics Ilaclari Ltd Sti., Türkiye produced by: World Medicine Ilac San. Ve Tic. A.S. Türkiye

41	MIDRIMAX Comb.drug (Phenylephrine hydrochloride, Tropicamide)	Eye drops 5 ml (bottles- droppers)	Sentiss Pharma Pvt. Ltd India
42	MOXY-D Comb.drug (Moxifloxacin hydrochloride, Dexamethasone sodium phosphate)	Eye drops 10 ml (dropper bottles)	Laborate Pharmaceuticals India Ltd India
43	MOSI-D Comb.drug (Moxifloxacin, dexamethasone)	Eye drops 5 ml N1 (dropper bottles)	FDC Limited India
44	TIMATE Timolol maleate	Eye drops 0.5% 5 ml N1 (dropper bottles)	AXA PARENTERALS LTD India
45	TIMOLENS Timolol	Eye drops 5 mg/ml 5 ml (vials)	Belinda Limited, Great Britain produced by: Balkanpharma Razgrad AD Bulgaria
46	TIMOLOL- ORVILLE Timolol maleate	Eye drops 0.5% 5 ml (vials droppers)	Aristopharma Ltd Bangladesh
47	TIMORITE Timolo	Eye drops 0.5% 5 ml N1 (vials)	VIV Life LLP., India manufactured by: Vivimed Labs Limited India
48	TIMOT Timolol	Eye drops 0.25% 5 ml (dropper bottles)	Swiss Parental Ltd. India
49	T-LOL Timolol	Eye drops 0.5% 5 ml (dropper bottles)	Life Pharma Systems LLP, Great Britain manufactured by Divine Laboratories Pvt. Ltd India
50	TOBRA-D Comb.drug (Tobramycin sulfate, Dexamethasone sodium phosphate)	Drops eye and ear 10 ml (plastic bottles)	Laborate Pharmaceuticals India Ltd India
51	TOBRASON	Eye drops 5 ml (dropper bottles)	Amman Pharmaceutical Industries Co. Jordan

	Comb.drug (Dexametazone, Tobramycin)		
52	TOBRIMED Tobramycin	Eye drops 0.3% 5 ml (dropper bottle)	World Medicine İlaç San. ve tick. A.Ş. Türkiye
53	TOBROM Tobramycin	Eye drops 0.3% 5 ml (bottle)	S.C. Rompharm Company S.R.L. Romania
54	TRAVAPRESS ROMPHARM Travoprost	Eye drops 0.04 mg/ml 2.5 ml N1 (dropper bottle)	S.C.Rompharm Company S.R.L. Romania
55	PHENIDEX Comb.drug (Dexametasone,chlor amphenicol)	Eye drops 10 ml (dropper bottles)	Amman Pharmaceutical Industries Co. Jordan
56	FILARMEX Comb.drug (Dexamethasone, neomycini sulfas, polymyxini B sulfas)	Eye drops 5 ml N1 (dropper bottles)	Belinda Laboratories LLP, Great Britain produced: Balkanpharma–Razgrad AD Bulgaria
57	FOTIL® FORTE Comb.drug (Timolol maleate, pilocarpine)	Eye drops 5 ml (bottles)	Santen Oy, Finland manufactured by: NextPharma Oy Finland
58	FOTYL® Comb.drug (Timolol maleate, pilocarpine)	Eye drops 5 ml (bottles)	Santen Oy, Finland manufactured by: NextPharma Oy Finland
59	FUTARON Fusidic acid*	Eye drops, suspension 1% 5 g N1 (dropper bottles)	World Medicine Ophthalmics İlaçları Ltd. Turkey produced by: World Medicine İlac San. ve Tic. A.S. Türkiye
60	HYLORA sodium hyaluronate	Eye drops 0.15% 10 ml N1 (dropper bottles)	World Medicine Ophthalmics İlaçları Ltd. Sti., Türkiye produced by: World Medicine İlac San. ve Tic. A.Ş. Türkiye
61	CYCLOMED Cyclopentolate	Eye drops 1% 5 ml (dropper bottles)	Sentiss Pharma Pvt. Ltd India
62	EMOPROKS(Emopr oks) Methylethylpyridinol	Eye drops 1% 5 ml (dropper bottle)	World Medicine Ophthalmics İlaçları Ltd. Sti., Türkiye produced by: World Medicine İlac San. ve Tic. A.S. Türkiye

63	TRAVAPRESS DUO Comb.drug (Travoprost, timolol)*	Eye drops 2.5 ml (dropper bottle) S.C.Rompharm Company S.R.L. Romania	Sante (Private) Limited., Pakistan Made: Elko Organization (Pvt.) Ltd Pakistan
64	DEXATOBROM Comb.drug (Tobramycin,dexame thasone)	Eye drops-suspension 5 ml (dropper bottle)	Rompharm Company SRL Romania
65	PHENIDEX Comb.drug (Dexametasone,chlor amphenicol)	Eye drops 10 ml (dropper bottles)	Amman Pharmaceutical Industries Co. Jordan

As can be seen from the data in Table 3, an analysis of the range of medicines for ophthalmic diseases included in the State Register of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2022 showed that medicines from foreign manufacturers comprise 65 items, of which 64 are eye drops (vials), 1 gel.

Fig.3 Quantitative ratio of registered medicines used in ophthalmic diseases.

The diagram shows the proportion of registered medicines used for ophthalmic diseases in foreign countries.

Fig.4 Quantitative ratio of registered medicines used in ophthalmic diseases.

The diagram shows the quantitative ratio of registered medicines used for ophthalmic diseases in domestic production, CIS countries and in foreign countries, produced in vials and tubes.

DISCUSSION. Thus, the study of the data of the “State Register of medicines, medical devices and medical equipment approved for use in medical practice of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2022 No. 26 showed that the share of medicines used for ophthalmic diseases produced in domestic countries is up to 18 names of medicines, manufacturers of the CIS countries registered 21 medicines, medicines of manufacturers of foreign countries amounted to 65 names.

An analysis of the conjuncture of medicines used in ophthalmic diseases showed that in the pharmaceutical market of Uzbekistan, herbal products are represented by such dosage forms as drops (vials), ointments and gels. The total number of registered drugs amounted to 104 items, of which 102 items are in the form of a vial of dosage forms.

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